

PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING THE SOCIO-POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Annotation

The article highlights the issues of women's activity as a subject in the public administration system, creating the basis for performing certain tasks in the public administration system as an object, that is, they bring their functions to the management system, that it consists of functions expressing the socio-demographic status, social-political aspirations of women, creating the necessary conditions for the realization of their dreams.

Key words: public administration, women, socio-political institutions, functional features of the management system, needs and requirements of objects, socio-political aspirations, social activity, socio-political being, socio-political life, the art of management.

The functioning of women as a subject in the system of public administration is closely related to the functions before social and political institutions. When women participate in the state management system, they must first of all be well aware of the functional features of this management system and the technology of their implementation.

Since the main principle of a democratic state is to serve people, it is undoubtedly obliged to take into account the needs and requirements of all objects. Therefore, women, both as objects and as people, put their demands and needs before the management, and want their satisfaction. This creates the basis for them to set certain tasks to the public administration system as objects, that is, they bring their functions to the administration system. In our opinion, these tasks consist of the functions arising from the following social and demographic status of women.

1. Ensuring the socio-political, economic and cultural rights of women.
2. Establishing gender equality in the family, fight against discrimination.
3. Greater involvement of women in the management of state and community affairs.
4. Help to improve the management system.
5. To achieve the development of civil institutions.
6. Contribute to the education of the young generation by organizing spiritual and educational events.

It can be seen that with these functions, women help the public administration system to fully fulfill social tasks, and even take over some of its functions.

Mandatory functions of the state administration system and voluntary functions of women are dialectically related to each other according to their substantial importance, origin and impact on social and political existence. If women are forced to take on the functions of the public administration system as a responsible employee, leader, member of the organization (then women are responsible for performing the mandatory functions of the public administration system), and as public members and activists, they also bring their

voluntary functions into the operation of the administration system. . Mandatory functions apply to more responsible women, and voluntary functions to public, active women. However, although mandatory functions are not visible, they do not affect the activities of public women, the content and organization of activities. The influence of public women on social and political existence is determined by their correct understanding of mandatory functions and their contribution to their fulfillment. Therefore, the voluntary functions of public women as an expression of their socio-political activity affect the entire management system and its effective operation. Only a woman who is able to combine her voluntary functions and public activities with the mandatory functions of the state administration system becomes a subject who creates, if necessary, changes, renews or develops the socio-political existence. So, the subject is not just an activity, but a person who actively affects the social and political existence, the state management system.

The state management system of women and girls has a cratological essence (state significance) as an active subject of socio-political existence. When the new state administration system is being formed, the socio-political activity of citizens and the role of democratic values in the decision-making process are of incomparable importance.

Creating the necessary conditions for the realization of women's socio-political aspirations and dreams, their objectification is important for both women and the state administration system. If women have the opportunity to express themselves, express their existing knowledge, experience and potential, and develop them further, the state administration system will serve the interests of the general population, prove in practice that it is the power of the people, and raise the political culture of women.

The state, its management system, and social management in general have not left anyone indifferent, because the activities of these institutions are related to the life and destiny of people, people, and the nation. That is why women, especially their socio-politically active part, contribute to solving the problems of socio-political existence. At the same time, socio-political activity is not "born" in a person ready-made, like Plato's "minemsis". It is a quality that can be formed and inculcated into the human mind, behavior and lifestyle through social educational means. This is often done by the state and its institutions. In scientific literature, it is called "political socialization" [1. 212]. So, objectification, political socialization is an objective necessity for state management and social development.

The relationship of women and girls to the social and political existence encourages them to know and study their social characteristics, which ensure their effective participation in state administration. The polyfunctional reality and complexity of socio-political life, state administration imposes certain demands on the social characteristics of women, because the object encountered, a person, cannot take over the state administration, he cannot successfully perform it, for this he depends not only on personal (individual), but also on social characteristics, characteristics must have.

The place and status of women in the socio-political existence depends on their political culture. Doctor of Philosophy, professor B. T. Toychiev writes that political culture is directly related to the economic system of society, and it is formed under the influence of all spheres of spiritual life [2. 30]. "Political culture," writes B.T. Toychiev, "is the basis of the priority principles for people's political behavior, the value system that ensures its organization to the community."

It organizes social institutions and organizations as priority principles, social norms and ideals for political behavior, ensures mutual influence, expresses the integral and integrative nature of the political sphere..." [3. 34]. At the same time, the scientist emphasizes that political culture is a reality that is related to political consciousness, political knowledge, political experience and integrates other spheres of human activity. So, since there is no pure political reality, politics is essentially related to the life of society and the state, social and political activity should be considered from the point of view of the integrative nature of political culture.

While working in the state administration system, women face various spheres of social life, they are forced to solve the problems in them, and the solution of these problems is always of socio-political importance. Political culture means to be well aware of the most important scientific and theoretical teachings about the society and the state, the Constitution of the country and the most important laws. Without knowing the political and legal norms that apply to the society and the state, it is impossible to interfere in the management system, manage and conduct the affairs of the society and the state [4. 44-45]. Therefore, the acquisition of political culture is a guarantee of successful socio-political activity.

The next sign that ensures women's socio-political activity is quality, that is, their professional, professional knowledge. Although there is an inextricable connection between professional work, knowledge and socio-political activity, the former does not always lead to the successful conduct of the socio-political sphere and activity. Socio-political activity requires getting out of the scope of narrow professional occupation and knowledge, that is, having a wide experience of society and state life.

As the object of the state administration system is people, the subject of socio-political activity is interpersonal relations. Socio-political activism requires a good knowledge of human and interpersonal relations, their influence on socio-political existence and processes. Therefore, the next social sign of socio-political activity is to know the human relations of women, the features of manifestation of the fundamental goals based on them in everyday life, and finally, the dynamics of social relations and human psychology.

Giving in to spiritual and spiritual calls, passions and callings is a characteristic of women. This situation means that they are easily exposed to external influences, socio-political activity often requires coolness, boldness, taking responsibility and using unusual methods.

A female leader or a socio-politically active subject has not only her own psychological characteristics, but also her own style of management, technology, i.e. management culture. In these immanent characteristics of her there are aspects that differ from those of men. That is why scientific literature mentions the existence of fields such as "women's psychology", "women's management", "woman-leader".

Women's gentleness in management work, overindulgence in feelings, thinking about their family and children even in the process of work are not their shortcomings, but their own internal, immanent characteristics, even achievements. In this place, the characteristics and virtues typical of Eastern women can be seen.

American researcher, business theorist and psychologist Pat Williams in his book "Paradoxes of Power" calls Jesus a true leader, who achieved unprecedented success, "a genius manager who achieved power without power, who was strong without power." "He wins without fighting, his greatness is in serving people, his genius is in his simplicity, and he

lives even though he is dead" [5. V. 20]. Isn't it paradoxical that he won a victory without a fight and that his ideas are uniting people even though he is dead? Pat Williams calls Jesus' rule over people's thoughts, wills and lives, leading and organizing them a paradox, because there are few people like Jesus who united millions of people around him and formed human relationships between them. That is why more than 1.5 billion people in the world believe in Judaism and follow its teachings.

Another American researcher, well-studied the psychology of people and power, Robert Green, the author of the works "48 Laws of Power" and "50 Laws of Power", known to the world and the world of science because of them, the secret of uniting and managing people is knowing their wishes, desires and needs. , believes that. "Management is the art of charming and taming people. Whoever knows and masters this art will undoubtedly achieve success" [6. 63]. Therefore, the art of management, the success of women in the socio-political existence, is primarily to ensure the dialectical unity and harmony of subject-object relations.

Achieving the social activity of women requires, first of all, ensuring their employment, involving them in economic relations, market economy. No social activity is formed outside of these relationships. Only the subject who has his own job, property, and place in economic life correctly perceives the concerns of the society, finds and proposes mechanisms for improving the state management system. True, women are far from accepting economic activity as a reality with a socio-political character. Their ownership of private property is dominated by individuality, that is, private property is viewed primarily as a source of improving the material condition of the family. "Women tend to look at private property as a source of improving their family and financial conditions, not for expanding it further, creating new products, opening new jobs and achieving a stable position in the region or industry. For them, the first task is not the general socio-economic development, but the well-being of family life" [7. 116-117]. Similarly, women put the factor of increasing family well-being higher than social and political interests. It is necessary to absolutely condemn this familism in them, not to consider it as something that is against development, but family well-being is the source and indicator of the development of society.

Today, almost all parties have a woman as their deputy leader, and they have women's wings. About 700 non-governmental non-profit organizations deal with women's issues. In February 2019, in order to coordinate the activities of NGOs and exchange experience between them, to improve the base of social services, a republican women's forum was held in February 2019 on the topic "The experience of non-governmental non-profit organizations in increasing the social and political activity of women". NGO Club" was established.

Today, the number of members of this club has reached 58. Also, a cluster of social services was developed within this Club.

A legal clinic for women was established in cooperation with NGOs in the Republics of Kashkadarya, Khorezm, Fergana and Karakalpakstan.

In order to improve the activities of NGOs and established shelters, to strengthen their material and technical base, UNICEF provided material support in the amount of 56,000 US dollars.

Social and political activities of women are objective in nature. But at the same time, the fact that women themselves are socio-political activists and try to get out of a difficult social situation is the golden rule of increasing the effectiveness of the social protection system for women, and it shows the subjective aspect of this activism, their approach to social life, their

life experience. , also explained by the interaction of various social entities. In addition, it should not be forgotten that this activity has an individual character. Because the activity of each woman depends on her individual characteristics, in particular, her initiative, level of socio-political consciousness, intellectual potential, hard work, spiritual and moral qualities, etc.

Protection of women's rights and freedoms and legal interests is becoming more important in the current era of globalization. Increasing social-economic and political-legal activity of women in particular is becoming a demand of the times. Today, about 1,400 women are working in leadership positions in the system of state and public organizations in our country. Among women, 17 senators are working in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis, and 21 deputies are working in the Legislative Chamber. Women make up more than 23 percent of people's representatives in local councils. 1 thousand 25 women were elected to the post of chairpersons of self-governing agencies in the elections held in May of this year for the chairmanship of citizens' assemblies. The number of women managers working in various enterprises in our country is also increasing. This indicator was 44.2 percent in 2017, and reached 45.3 percent in 2019. The share of women in health care and social services is more than 82 percent, in the fields of science, education, culture and art - 72 percent, in agriculture - more than 45 percent, and in industry - 38 percent. The share of women entrepreneurs in the total number of business entities in our country is 29 percent" [8]. The scope of the conducted sociological research is very wide, and they lead to the improvement of the management system not only in the neighborhood, in organizations, but also in the whole society, and at the same time, to increase the effectiveness of the social protection system of women in Uzbekistan to the level required by the times.

Women's activism, as a type of social activism, first of all covers the social sphere of society, but at the same time, it is manifested in any type of social activity and goes beyond the boundaries of the purely social sphere. That is, political activity is always socially oriented and focused on satisfying important social interests and develops under the influence of socio-economic, organizational-political, socio-psychological, socio-demographic, material-household, cultural-technical and other factors.

The problem of increasing women's activity has taken a wide place in the research of researchers. In the works of the philosopher and scientist M. Kholmatova, this situation is analyzed from the point of view of socio-historical and woman's position in society and family. Uzbek families, which are part of the Eastern family, have a tradition of fulfilling all their duties and responsibilities based on mutual respect, strict internal discipline, and showing kindness and kindness to each other [9. 59].

This universal feature is characteristic of the ethnoculture of Uzbek women. Scientist O. Nishonova, who conducted research in this regard, said: "In the ethnoculture of Uzbek women, the unique lifestyle, life experience, customs, traditions of intergenerational communication, understanding of the world, ways of perceiving the world, family and household rituals, spiritual wealth, social norms, examples of cultural creativity are collected" [10. 21].

Increasing the socio-political activity of women as a component of the reforms implemented in our country is inextricably linked with the development of society and the improvement of the effectiveness of their social protection system. These are:

- 1) ensuring women's interests, needs, rights and freedoms, women's active participation in state administration;
- 2) ensure their employment;
- 3) social protection of women in severe social situation;
- 4) prevention of women's delinquency and criminality;
- 5) ensuring the stability of the spiritual environment in the family.

In conclusion, it should be noted that these factors are important in increasing and improving the active participation of women in the social and political life of the society, and serve to increase the level of their social protection.

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